

Addressing Environmental Challenges in Nigeria's Niger Delta Through Innovative Solution in Ogaga Ifowodo Poetry

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Abstract

This paper will explore selected poems of the Nigerian poet and activist, Ogaga Ifowodo, in order to highlight the writer's yet under-researched but invaluable contributions to the country's evolving environmental challenges in the oil-rich region. Following a concise survey of existing commentary on Ifowodo's works, there is a common thread that is shared in this corpus within the larger context of eco-criticism and social responsibility that currently exist between oil-producing communities and the multinational oil corporation. Ifowodo's petro fiction narratives and eco-criticism deserve greater scholastic attention and scrutiny for the way in which they imaginatively document the tumultuous political repression in Nigeria during the 1980s and 1990s. Furthermore, the paper demonstrated that his engagement with the ecological and socio-economic fall-out of oil exploration in the country's Niger Delta region from which he hails marks his oeuvre as a unique and innovative contribution to the contemporary reconstructions of Nigerian nationhood situated in the intersections between literary historicisation, political resistance as well as cultural and eco-critical activism.

Keywords: Eco-criticism, Petro fiction, Niger Delta region, Exploration, Political repression.

Abbreviations

TOL: The Oil Lamp

Introduction

The aim of this study is to examine, critically, how the poetry of Ogaga Ifowodo, who was born in 1966 in Oleh, Delta State of Nigeria, have operated in the context of protest, against the key social and political challenges in Nigeria during the military dictatorship. This study offers readings of the works by poet from a comparative viewpoint, using poetic voice and political struggle as his strong point. Additionally, references to the South African anti-apartheid struggle to be found in Ifowodo's poems in

Madiba and The Oil Lamp make intertextual analysis especially relevant.

Some of the selected poems from Ifowodo's works include: 'Jese', 'Odi', 'Cesspit of the Niger Delta', and 'A Good Mourning'. (Ogbinaka, 2022)

Furthermore, Ogbinaka continued that in West Africa, the post-independence era was characterised by several socio-political crises in places like Nigeria, Ghana, and Mali. This was reflected in the literature arising from the sub-region that highlighted some of the thematic concerns, tending to express disillusionment in societal expectations. Chinua

Achebe's *A Man of the People* and Ayi Kwei Armah's *The Beautiful Ones Are Not Yet Born* are two iconoclastic examples of novels written in that period (Lazarus, 1990), whose narratives outline some of the disappointments of the people's expectations. The themes of these novels are a series of protest writings in response to the failure of the subsequent postcolonial governments. The eventual outbreak of the Nigerian civil war in the late 1960s, due to the excesses of military officials and the horror of the military regime, resulted in more literary writings. Ken Saro-Wiwa's *Sozaboy*, Isidore Okpewho's *The Last Duty*, and John Pepper Clark's *The Wife's Revolt* are examples of works that portray the effects of the war.

Ken Wiwa (2001:45) situates the Niger Delta within the complex geography of Nigeria thus:

The Niger River Delta is the largest in Africa, 240 kilometers long north to south, and spreading along a 320-kilometers stretch of the southern coast of Nigeria. It extends over an area of dense rainforest covered by an intricate pattern of tributaries, streams rivers, creeks and mangrove swamps that is rich in natural resources — timber, coal, palm oil, and crude oil. It is one of the world's great ecosystem, and is often described as the heart and lungs of Nigeria.

The region can also be defined as the territory contained between the coastline of the Bights of Benin and Bonny (formerly Biafra) in the Gulf of Guinea. Writers from this region have explored

protest as a theme in various genres. Most of these writers have expressed their misgivings through their poems and plays over the marginalisation and exploitation of the Niger Delta region by government. Some of the most notable writers from the region who are poets include Ifowodo, Clark, Ken Saro-Wiwa, Tanure Ojaide, and Ebi Yeibo. There are also fiction writers such as Isidore Okpewho, Kaine Agary, and Vincent Egbuson, while the likes of Benedict Binebai, Esiaba Irobi and Peter Omoko are playwrights. Most of their works respond to the reckless and devastating effects of crude oil exploitation in the area by oil multinationals in collaboration with several military and civilian governments. Over the decades there has been massive environmental pollution and degradation of the ecosystem leading to the ruin of farmlands and fishing waters which are the major sources of livelihood for the locals. According to Joseph Ushie (2011:528),

The emergence of Niger Delta writing in the wake of the scandalous exploration for and exploitation of oil mineral resource in a life-threatening manner ... explains the qualification of the Niger Delta literature under consideration here with the adjective 'protest', to distinguish it from other kinds of literary art from this region.

Significantly, Peter Omoko (2018:212) observes that the protest against oil exploitation in the region 'has

engaged writers and critics alike and may probably have overtaken the output of apartheid literature in South Africa'. The late 1980s marked a change in the mode of writing by some poets of the Niger Delta region with themes ranging from cultural, ritual, and archetypal traditions to those of protest and resistance, with less emphasis on the structure and other unifying devices of poetry. The evolution in themes of protest and resistance in poetry among some of the poets in the Niger Delta region is perceived as 'residing within the conflicting terrain of the unresolved; acknowledging incoherence and contradictions in the writing of poetry' (Garuba, 2005:65). It is interesting to note that their poetry is mostly written in English which is a language for teaching and learning in the region. Some of the poetry that comes out of the Niger Delta region are like the protest literature of South Africa during the struggle for liberation.

Ifowodo became a student union activist as an undergraduate and, upon graduation, he worked as a human rights activist. He was arrested in 1997 while returning from the Commonwealth Heads of Government Summit in Scotland, having called for stronger sanctions against the military regime of Sani Abacha, the same dictator who had hanged Saro-Wiwa, the renowned Niger Delta poet, playwright, and activist in 1995. Ifowodo was set free from prison in 1998 following local and international campaigns for the release of detained writers, which included the likes of Akin Adesokan and Nnimmo

Bassey (Okunoyè, 2011). Ifowodo has won various awards which include: the 1993 Association of Nigerian Authors (ANA) poetry prize; the 2003 ANA/Cadbury Poetry Prize; the 2005 Gabriel Okpara Poetry Prize, and the 1996 Association of Nigerian Authors Prize for Poetry, and the manuscript of the poems entitled 'Red Rain' won a national prize in 1998 before it was published as for *Homeland and Other Poems*.

Pius Adesanmi and Chris Dunton (2005:17) identify Ifowodo as belonging to the third generation of writers in Nigeria whose formation was

marked by more than two decades of military despotism in Nigeria, the highpoint of which was the illegal detention of Ifowodo and Akin Adesokan by the regime of the late Abacha in 1997.

Third-generation writers are defined by Adesanmi and Dunton as those 'who had acquired a creative identity markedly different from the second generation writers', such as Niyi Osunday, Ojaide, Odia Ofeimun, and Fetus Iyayi. They refer to the second-generation writers as those 'born into the colonial event but their formative years were mostly shaped by independence and its aftermath of disillusionment and stasis'.

Ifowodo has published four collections of poetry: *Homeland and Other Poems* (1998), which focuses on military rule in Nigeria; *Madiba* (2003), which captures the anger and hopes of his generation;

The Oil Lamp (2005), which bemoans the ecological devastation of the Niger Delta region; and A Good Mourning (2016), which protests against the oppressive acts of the military dictator, Ibrahim Babangida. Ifowodo has earned himself a reputation as the most committed Nigerian poet in his generation.

Idom Thomas Inyabri (2012:102) is one of the commentators who situate Ifowodo's poetry among the most aesthetic of his generation, pointing out the popularity of 'For Art's Sake'. Inyabri describes the poem as 'the option that gives sheer artistic pleasure to the listener/reader, even in the midst of pain'. Ifowodo's ability to show pain amidst his people's predicament retrieves humanity and moves the reader toward the brighter side of life. Ifowodo's poetry gained popularity in Nigeria from the late 1980s and is still being both read and produced in the present.

Babatunde Bakare (2017:19), in a similar view, agrees with A.N. Suhana when he recognises the relevance of works by some renowned Nigerian writers, such as Ola Rotimi, Wole Soyinka, Chinua Achebe, Femi Osofisan, John Pepper Clark, and Ben Okri. According to Bakare, the socio-political and economic reality of the present day that is central in the themes of their work is perhaps the main reason why theatre practitioners and scholars cannot but be associated with creating or re-inventing new works from their works. Such re-invention, he declares, has

led to world recognised achievements in their various works. Their work is not only acting as a template to these writers but as a reference point for critical minds and great thinkers in Nigeria and the entire world.

The trio of Christopher Ogunyemi, Abosede Otemuyiwa, and Niyi Akingbe (2011:308) situate post-colonial Nigerian society's experiences through Fetus Iyayi's Violence, as a dehumanising condition of living, of the masses; they approximate the concept of 'violence' as an expansive vocabulary for the description of economic exploitation. They strongly believe that things can be turned around through the interrogative power and protest of the masses. Post-colonial Nigerian literature is a literature of self-realisation, providing avenues for those frustrated by the bourgeois and government institutions.

Gbemisola Adeoti (2003:112) observes that the military interference in the Nigerian political space triggered a new literary experience when he writes:

Shortly after, it became increasingly clear that the military had no solution to the myriad of problems that it intervened to tackle; problems such as a parlous economy, decayed infrastructure, poverty, corruption, ethno-religious conflicts, and nepotism, among other ills.

It is not surprising, therefore, to perceive the twist of themes in the discourse of postcolonial Nigerian

literature, whether in verse, drama, or narrative fiction, bearing in mind the calibre of literary giants that pervades its sphere, in the likes of Christopher Okigbo, Chinua Achebe, Wole Soyinka, John Pepper Clark, Femi Osofisan, and Ken Saro-Wiwa. They were a few of the writers who confronted the excesses of the military rulers, especially when these rulers did not perform to the expectation of the citizens.

Adekunle Olowonmi's view (2008:57) in a way conforms those of Adeoti when he posits that the theory of military intervention in politics in Africa and other third world countries is a catalytic post-colonial discourse. He explains that the inability of the political elite to give the country the force to move forward and the failure of the political institutions to serve, heralded the first military coup in Nigeria 1966. The totalitarianism, oppressive disposition and tall orders given by the military further spurred the mood, temper, and spontaneous reaction of writers in the Nigerian literary scene.

Ayo Kehinde (2010:29) aligns himself with the notion of socio-political complexity in Nigerian society. He reveals how neo-colonial Nigerian rulers exclude some citizens from the utopian space of the public sphere in the country. It is for this reason, he argues, that Achebe's *Anthills of the Savannah*, Ben Okri's *The Famished Road* and Chimamanda Adichie's *Purple Hibiscus* yield singular insight into a theoretical understanding of the concept of the Public Sphere. He sums up: 'Nigerian postcolonial

fiction affords an indispensable medium for teasing out and exploring the fraught, antithetical meanings embedded within the notion of the Public Sphere, that is, human rights' (29). The post-colonial Nigerian writers have, in various works, written to criticise the unacceptable situation faced by the masses.

Agbada Nwachucku (1990:3) reveals that the anger of the post-war Nigerian poets not only stems from the failure of the elite culture, but also from the negative correlates of the Nigerian Civil War, the Niger Delta oil wealth euphoria, the ideology of capitalistic economic formation, and, principally, successive militaristic totalitarian dictatorships. He considers a line-up of challenges that became visible in the work of the post-war era poets of Nigeria, including that:

The pre-war poets may have perceived poorly, or in themselves were yet to "percolate" for intimate consideration, or possibly still were regarded as too common place to require his attention; tranny and oppression, corruption, suffering and persecution, ineffective public utility network, military intervention and military leadership.

Nwachucku's belief is that, for the post-war poet, these are issues of fundamental interest which writers can no longer avoid.

Oyeniye Okunoye (2008:2, 5) surveys the major themes dominating the Niger Delta literature which he defines as:

Assessing the social and economic realities that precipitated the collective revolt of the people after the late Ken Saro-Wiwa brought the plight of the Ogoni people to the attention of the international community.

He said this situation has necessitated unique contributions from the region's writers, making for a contemporary Nigerian poetry that has sustained a remarkable trans-ethnic literary practice. He identifies poets from this region as exploring the link between the shared agony of the people of the Niger Delta and a tradition of protest poetry that has been thriving in the region.

In his general appraisal of Nigerian literature, Sule Egya (2019:14) observes that modern writers in English are grouped into three generations for convenient categorisation, to which he refers as first, second and third. His categorisation is done in terms of historical epochs, and political and social contexts. The groups that he defines belong the periods known as the pre-independence era, the post-independence era, and the military era. Egya situates his categorisation in line with Garuba's (2005) delineation of the different generations in Nigerian poetry, which comprise the poets of the first generation or Modernist Nationalists, which includes

Gabriel Okara, Christopher Okigbo, and Wole Soyinka; the second generation or Marxist Nationalists, such as Odia Ofeimun, Niyi Osundare, and Tanure Ojaide; and the third generation, which includes poets who are much newer to the scene, the likes of Ogaga Ifowodo, and Ebi Yeibo.

Christain Opukri and Ibaba S. Ibaba (2008:174) survey the ecological degradation of the Niger Delta due to oil exploration, and they declare that the literature of the region highlights poverty, unemployment, underemployment, proletarianisation, and rural-urban migration as its consequences. However, they were not satisfied that the literature had adequately addressed the internal population displacement due to its ecological degradation, and the resultant productivity losses in the Niger Delta. The literature of the region has ceaselessly condemned all parties involved in the degradation of the region. The impact of their action has brought untold hardship to the citizens of the host communities.

Concurring with Okpuri and Ibaba, Akachi Odoemene (2011:129) comments that the 'diverse literature on the Niger Delta agrees that the oil industry has not promoted the development of the region; instead, it has undermined the area's human development'. He believes that the impact of the massive devastation on the region over time will certainly have various social consequences that will lead to human underdevelopment. A situation that

may translate into the devalued nature of human existence in the region.

The poem entitled 'Jese' is named for an oil-producing town in Delta State, Jesse, and it centres around a fiery inferno that occurred in the town. The deadly fire outbreak, which caused large-scale destruction of lives and properties, has been linked to negligence. The people of 'Jese', are directly affected by the pipeline explosion. The poem exposes the complicity with which the state and the oil company operated in the region. It addresses the public general regarding the negative impact of crude oil exploration on the people's condition of living and their environment. 'Jese' is a free verse poem structured into fifteen sequences from I-XV, with a continuous narrative of the Jesse fire episode.

In the opening of the poem, the speaker reveals the burden of fuel scarcity on the people:

*It was the fourteenth month of the fuel crunch
and stoves cooked cobwebs in cold corners.
Dreading the spirits that live in trees,
they would not break green twigs to make a meal,
till the fuel crunch compelled choice between
5
tree and human, today and tomorrow.*

The forest quivered as trunk after trunk snapped,
and a nameless rage wagged green-fingered

branches in the air as they fell to the hungry axe.
(TOL, 3)

The speaker exposes the hardship caused by the scarcity of petroleum products. In line 1 above, the speaker refers to a prolonged period of suffering due to a shortage of fuel. In line 2, he metaphorically equates the idle 'stoves' with the cooking of 'cobwebs' in 'cold corners' of the kitchen. This implies that 'stoves' had not been used in a long time, so spiders had built 'cobwebs' there. In lines 3 and 4, the speaker uses a third-person narrative voice, 'they', to express aspects of a myth to explain a part of the people's cultural beliefs.

Harold Scheub (1985:3) claims that:

Myth is not a tale; it is a process within a tale. It is related to stories of the gods because gods are creators and are thus involved in primal transitions...Myth is a metaphor, and because of that it is a narrative device, but it is more. Ancient motifs, condensed, symbolic, heavy with emotional potential, are embedded in the tradition; myth has the power to activate those motifs, to release and contain the intense feelings. Always in motion, myth is liberating, but its leap into the unknown, in the oral tradition, seldom open-ended.

The assumptions of myth sometimes manifest from people's sub consciousness because such assumptions influence reasoning and are, therefore, a significant aspect of imagination. Myths also constitute cultural ties between people and

supernatural beliefs. The 'dreading [of] the spirits that live in trees' also suggests that 'the fuel crunch' erodes the mythological and cultural beliefs of the people. The 'green twigs' are probably the only option left for the women to make meals. Lines 5 and 6 suggest the hard 'choice' people had to make between nurturing the environment and destroying it to stay alive. The 'compelled choice' is, presumably, the scooping of fuel from leaking pipes as an option to light up stoves, rather than use the 'green twigs' to make meals, so increasing the risk of uncontrolled fire. This explains the dilemma of the people.

The consonants in the phrase 'rage wagged green-fingered' depict the falling of trees to the 'hungry axe'. The sequences of the 'g' sound in the consonants evoke the rhythmic effect of swinging branches of trees as 'trunk after trunk' is snapped. In the stanzas that follow, the speaker reveals the people's choice of cooking energy:

They smelt edible death in food cooked
10
with logs still so alive they hissed,
then puffed out clouds of wet smoke so bitter

the women wept into their pots.
In the fourteenth month of the fuel crunch,
with oil lamps dry and dusty, nightfall
15
wrapped their village in a veil of ink.

*They turned to candles till their need made wax gold,
forcing them to roost earlier than their hens*

*on moonless nights when fireflies mocked
the dimmed promise of eletiriki.*

20 (TOL, 3)

In lines 10-13, the speaker personifies the logs in 'hissed' and 'puffed'. The onomatopoeic word 'hissed' evokes the sound emitted by the logs, expressing their disdain at being used in such a manner. Line 13 shows the use of fresh sun-dried twigs, which produce a lot of smoke; hence 'the women wept into their pots' as their eyes water. The cruelty in burning 'logs still so alive' constitutes damage done to the broader ecosystem as well as local environmental degradation. In the absence of dry 'logs', the women resort to 'green twigs' as cooking energy to survive the 'fuel crunch'. Lines 15 and 16 suggest that the 'oil lamps' have not been used in a long time and that the people live in darkness.

Madam Edoja laments the havoc that oil exploration wreaks in the next stanzas:

Oil is my curse, oil is our doom.
Where is my husband, where is my love?
At the bottom of the sea, the bottom of the sea.

Oil is my curse, oil is our doom.

Where is the fish for palm-oil soup?

210

Dead in the creeks, dead in the lakes.

Oh mate, do you have a cup of garri

to lend me for the children's sake?

Not even a cup, not even a handful! (TOL, 17)

The speaker presents the negative impact of crude oil exploration in the region through Edoja's experiences. The italicised stanzas above function like a dramatic monologue, exposing Edoja's lament about the decline in food and agricultural produce in the area. The rhetorical questions beg for answers about Edoja's helpless situation. These questions also indicate that people suffer due to the agricultural and aquatic devastations in the region. Edoja's lamentation changes the tone of the poem and changes the mood to one of sympathy. The repetition 'Oil is my curse' and 'oil is our doom' suggests the devastating effects of oil exploitation on the people of the region. Madam Edoja finds nothing good in oil, hence her lament.

The use of the possessive adjective 'my' suggests a sense of personal loss, as in the case of the death of her husband in a previous oil disaster, while the speaker's use of 'our' also refers to the collective loss suffered by all in the various oil disasters in the region. The land has become infertile and unable to

support vegetation, while the water is polluted and unable to support aquatic life. The shortage in 'fish' and the 'garri' (the local staple food) might be due to the spillage of oil on land and water. So 'Not even a cup, not even a handful' suggests food insufficiency and scarcity.

Edoja's travail shows the negative impact of crude oil on the people. Her name, 'Edoja', means 'the day of lament', which is apt, as she laments the torments she faces over the horrors of oil exploration in the region.

The next two stanzas of the poem are about the devastation of oil exploration on the land:

The fields are tarred where cassava once grew,

215

you know the fields are tarred and harder

than a shell, too hard for our hoes.

Oil is my curse, oil is my doom.

Where are my children? Where is my husband?

Ashes and bones. Ashes and bones.

220 (TOL, 17)

The italicised stanzas reflect Edoja's voice that decries the difficulty of cassava cultivation. Lines 215 and 216 show that plots of farmlands have been converted to a road leading to the oil company. The

two last lines of Edoja's lament connote hopelessness and the agony of death. The fire has a devastating effect on plants, animals, and the entire ecosystem.

The poem adapts oral poetic form to infuse elements of reality in the work. For instance, the opening line 'It was the fourteenth month of the fuel crunch' functions as a prologue, and the poem unfolds like a Griot narrating a story. The speaker presents his account of the poem like an eyewitness of an event. Janet Neith (2017:171) comments on the relevance of the speaker in the oral performance when she says: By choosing a speaker that neither witnesses nor participates in the event, he gives the audience a point of identification regardless of their own direct involvement.

The account of Madam Edoja's ordeal functions as an eyewitness account, infusing realism into the poem. Madam Edoja's song concludes the poem like a closing formula in oral performance. The song 'Oil is my curse, oil is our doom' aligns with the traditional oral performance, which is done in repetitive increments, narrating the sad tale and predicament that befalls her and others. The poem ends on a sad note, without a solution to the peoples' predicament.

In summary, Ifowodo as a poet from the region has pitched his tent with the suffering people rather than the rulers. The lack of electricity perhaps motivates the title of Ifowodo's book, *The Oil Lamp*, as a natural source of energy. The 'oil lamp' is also

referred to as a 'bush lamp' in the Delta region. It is a homemade lamp that is constructed with empty beverage cans with the wick piercing through the middle of the can's cover to draw the palm oil it uses as fuel. Even though palm oil is available locally as a source of energy for the lamp, its use is not recommended because it contributes to environmental pollution

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